

Climate_CRICES PROJECT

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D.1.4.2 Implementation of the Data Dashboard

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The purpose of this document is to give a description of the Climate_CRICES dashboard that was released on 30th April 2025 and is available [here](#).

The dashboard features representations of data and metadata related to the climate mitigation and adaptation policies that have been selected by each project partner in order to be analysed and enhanced with a data driven approach.

Besides multilingual data representations, the dashboard provides advanced functionalities to interact with data, such as cross filtering of visual objects and dynamic tuning of map representations. Moreover, it enables users to generate structured reports and export data visuals.

ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Definition
PP	Project Partner

1 INTRODUCTION AND OBJECTIVES

The document builds directly on the work carried out in the previous stages of the Climate_CRICES project.

In Deliverable D.1.3.1, the partnership comprehensively analysed existing climate information platforms at regional, national, and global levels, identifying key strengths and limitations in accessibility, policy integration, and user orientation. These findings informed the design principles of the dashboard.

In Deliverable D.1.3.2, a common metadata framework and indicator classification system were developed to structure policy content and datasets in a harmonized way. This formed the foundation for linking impacts, risks, indicators, and measures to meaningful data representations within the dashboard.

Deliverable D.1.3.3 detailed how system and user requirements were prioritized and translated into concrete dashboard functionalities. It also presented the rationale behind choosing a Power BI-based business intelligence approach—focusing on alphanumeric analysis and usability—over the originally proposed Web-GIS solution.

Deliverable D.1.4.2 now documents the implementation phase, demonstrating how all these elements— adaptation plans and data structuring, stakeholder needs, technical constraints, and usability targets—have been successfully integrated into the first release of the dashboard. The deliverable also outlines upcoming developments, ensuring continuity with the roadmap established in the earlier documents.

The dashboard was released on 30th April 2025 and it is freely accessible in any web browser [here](#). The current version of the dashboard meets the principal visualization and navigation requirement expressed by PPs, but in the near future it is going to be subject to further developments such as:

- new functionalities required by PP
- enhanced user experience and clearer data visualization
- contacts, FAQ and glossary sections
- translation of the whole content of the dashboard in all PPs' languages

Video tutorials on functionalities and contents of the dashboard were released when the dashboard was published, to facilitate its use. They are available in the project on-line repository [here](#).

While the collection and the upload of policies metadata for pilot regions is completed, the definition of the final list of datasets to be processed is under way. Therefore, the dashboard currently shows a small percentage of the available data. Nevertheless, as soon as the datasets are selected, they will be transformed and loaded in the dashboard during the project's lifetime.

The following paragraphs explain:

- the scope of the dashboard and the motivations that led to its current structure
- the content of the dashboard and its navigation scheme
- the main functionalities of the dashboard

2 SCOPE OF THE DASHBOARD

According to the application form, the main scope of the dashboard is to enable its users to analyse and compare climate adaptation and mitigation policies in order to find their strengths and weaknesses.

The final goal is to generate an addendum to help decision-makers in drafting and reviewing climate policies according to a data driven approach.

Considering the described context, PPs agreed that the pivotal entity of the dashboard should be policies instead of datasets.

In order to effectively transpose the information contained in policies into the dashboard, the following entities have been identified as significant for data collection:

- Policies
- Objectives
- Measures
- Actions
- Response indicators
- Impacts and Risks
- Impact indicators
- Datasets
- Areas, regions and other geographical entities

All of the defined entities are related to each other according to the diagram represented in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Overview of the entity relationship model

2.1 CONTENTS AND NAVIGATION SCHEME

2.1.1 HOME PAGE

The dashboard features a home page linking to four different sections (Figure 2):

- Regions
- Policies
- Impacts
- Indicators

Figure 2: The dashboard homepage

The Climate_CRICES project (*Increasing Climate Change Resilience in Central Europe*), funded by the Interreg CENTRAL EUROPE Programme (2024–2026), supports regional and local authorities in developing effective responses to climate change impacts (see pilot areas and countries in Figure 3). It focuses on integrating and visualizing underused environmental and meteorological data to improve decision-making for adaptation planning. By developing a multilingual, user-friendly data dashboard, the project enables better understanding and management of climate-related challenges such as heatwaves, floods, and climate change impacts on biodiversity.

More information: [Climate_CRICES project website](#)

Figure 3 - Central Europe Countries and Climate_CRICES Project pilot areas

As per the Climate_CRICES glossary the above terms are defined as follows:

- **Policies:** In the context of the Climate_CRICES project policy refers to the analysed climate change adaptation strategies of the pilot regions. These are documents managing the expected impacts of climate change, grounded on projections and expected impacts of climate change.
- **Impacts:** The consequences of realized risks on natural and human systems, where risks result from the interactions of climate-related hazards (including extreme weather/climate events), exposure, and vulnerability. Impacts generally refer to effects on lives, livelihoods, health and well-being, ecosystems and species, economic, social and cultural assets, services (including ecosystem services), and infrastructure. Impacts may be referred to as consequences or outcomes and can be adverse or beneficial.
- **Indicators:** Indicators are observable and measurable characteristics that can be used to simplify information to help understand the state of a concept or phenomenon, and/or to monitor it over time to show changes or progress towards achieving a specific change.

2.1.2 REGIONS

In this section it is possible to access all available information about one specific region (currently only pilot regions are available).

The screenshot shows the 'Regions' page of the Interreg Central Europe portal. At the top, there is a green header with the 'Regions' title and the Interreg Central Europe logo. Below the header is a navigation bar with buttons for 'HOME', 'Regions', 'Policies', 'Impacts', and 'Indicators'. A 'Climate_CRICES' button is also visible. The main content area features a list of countries on the left: AUSTRIA, CROATIA, CZECH REPUBLIC, GERMANY, HUNGARY, ITALY, and POLAND. In the center, there is a map of Central Europe with several regions highlighted in green. To the right of the map, there are three buttons: 'Regional Summary', 'Regional Datasets', and 'Compare Regions'. The footer contains links for 'Contacts', 'FAQ', and 'Glossary', and is powered by CSI.

Figure 4: View of the 'regions' page

By selecting a region, it is possible to access a summary of the available information about policies, indicators and datasets related to that region.

Figure 5: Regional summaries provide an overview of the policies, indicators and data availability for each.

Moreover, a data summary for indicators is available for each region.

Data Summary

Indicator

Cooling degree days

Year

2011 - 2020

Values by Municipality

Development in Time

List of Available Datasets

Figure 6: Visualization of available data

It is also possible to compare two regions in order to assess differences in the definition of their climate policies or the availability of regional datasets

Figure 7: Comparison of available info across two regions.

2.1.3 POLICIES

In this section it is possible to access all available information about one specific policy.

Policies

HOME Regions **Policies** Impacts Indicators

Country: Tutte Region: Tutte Coverage Area: Tutte [Clear all filters](#)

select a policy

Country	Coverage Area	Policy
CROATIA	City of Zagreb	1. Sustainable energy transition and climate change adaptation plan (SECAP)
CZECH REPUBLIC	Liberecky Region	Action plan for adaptation to climate change in the Liberec region (2021)
CZECH REPUBLIC	Hradek nad Nisou	Hrádek nad Nisou - Climate change adaptation strategy (2015)
CZECH REPUBLIC	Sub-basin of the Lusatian Neisse	Plan of the sub-basin of the Lusatian Neisse and other tributaries of the Oder (2021-2027)

[See details of the policy](#)

[Compare Policies](#)

[Contacts](#) [FAQ](#) [Glossary](#)

Powered by CSI

Figure 8: Policy selection landing page

By selecting a policy, it is possible to access a detailed description and all the available information about indicators and datasets related to that policy.

Policy Detail
Interreg CENTRAL EUROPE Co-funded by the European Union

← ↑ Compare to other policies
Climate_CRICES

SRACC (Regional Climate Change Adaptation Strategy)

Veneto Region		ITALY		
Coverage Area		Country		
37	48	N/A	25	13
Objectives	Measures	Actions	Covered Impacts	Covered Indicators

Description

The regional climate change adaptation strategy is currently in the approval phase. The process for its definition began with Veneto Regional Council deliberation no. 143 of November 30, 2021, which approved the Regional Economic and Financial Document for the 2022-2024 period, envisaging, among other initiatives, the preparation of a Regional Climate Change Adaptation Strategy. Subsequently, Veneto Regional Junta deliberation no. 705 of June 14, 2022, approved a collaboration with ARPAV for the development of the strategy. Further progress was made with Veneto Regional Junta deliberation no. 459 of May 29, 2024, which adopted the preliminary document of the Regional Climate Change Adaptation Strategy, marking a crucial step toward its final approval. Between July 11 and 24, 2024, thematic discussion meetings were held with key stakeholders, involving authorities, the planning and infrastructure sectors, economic operators, associations, and third-sector entities. The discussions focused on the urban sphere, the mountain and rural context with an emphasis on forests and agriculture, and the coastal and lagoon areas with attention to water resources. Furthermore, the strategy was subject to public consultation from May 14 to July 31, 2024, allowing citizens to participate in the decision-making process.

Figure 9: Page showing detailed information about the selected policy

It is also possible to compare two policies in order to assess differences in the definition of objectives, measure and actions or the availability of regional datasets.

Figure 10: Comparative analysis of information related to two policies of choice.

2.1.4 IMPACTS AND INDICATORS

These two sections are closely related, since they display a commonly defined list of impacts and indicators.

Impacts

HOME Regions Policies **Impacts** Indicators

Classification: Tutte Impact: Tutte

Clear all filters

Classification Level 1	Classification Level 2	Impact
Biodiversity	Terrestrial ecosystems	Change in climatic suitability for broadleaf and needleleaf trees
Biodiversity	Terrestrial ecosystems, Freshwater ecosystems	Changes in phenology
Heat & Drought, Flooding	Water scarcity, Heavy precipitation events	Health risks from water pollution exposure and sanitation in cities
Heat & Drought	Heatwaves, Coastal	Impacts of climate change on heating and cooling energy demand

select an impact

See details of the impact

See impact indicators

See impact indicators

Contacts FAQ Glossary

Powered by CSI

Figure 11: View of the 'impacts' landing page

By selecting an impact or an indicator, it is possible to access their detailed description and all the available information about policies and datasets related to them.

Health risks from water pollution exposure and sanitation in cities

Heat & Drought, Flooding

Classification - Level 1

Water scarcity, Heavy precipitation events

Classification - Level 2

5

Total impact indicators

5

Indicators with available data

6

Total impacted pilot areas

6

P. areas where impact is relevant

Description

Increased environmental health risks when using polluted groundwater. Vulnerability of users such as women, children, the elderly, ill or disabled. Decreased regional precipitation and changes in runoff and storage from droughts impairs the quality of water available. Less runoff to freshwater rivers can increase salinity, and concentrate pathogens and pollutants.

Figure 12: View of the detailed description of the selected impact

Moreover, a data summary is available for each indicator.

Data Summary

Indicator

Cooling degree days

Year

2011 - 2020

Values by Municipality

Development in Time

List of Available Datasets

Figure 13: Visualization of one of the datasets provided for the case of Saxony

By selecting an indicator, it is also possible to access the detailed data representations over two different pages:

- Quantitative data representation: showing different aggregations of the original data
- Geographical data representation: showing detailed data on a continuous map

Quantitative Data Representation
Interreg CENTRAL EUROPE Co-funded by the European Union

Cooling degree days

Municipalities by Avg. Cooling Degree Days (higher to lower) [1,2]

Coswig 110,80 Average Cooling Degree Days
Radebeul 108,08 Average Cooling Degree Days
Trebsen/Mulde 105,70 Average Cooling Degree Days
Bennewitz 105,54 Average Cooling Degree Days

Decade	Region	County	Municipality	Average Cooling Degree Days	Unit
1991 - 2000	Sachsen	N.A.		55,21	°C*days
2001 - 2010	Sachsen	N.A.		51,88	°C*days
2011 - 2020	Sachsen	N.A.		69,51	°C*days
1991 - 2000	Sachsen	Vogtlandkreis	Adorf/Vogtl.	30,12	°C*days
2001 - 2010	Sachsen	Vogtlandkreis	Adorf/Vogtl.	27,67	°C*days
2011 - 2020	Sachsen	Vogtlandkreis	Adorf/Vogtl.	42,38	°C*days
1991 - 2000	Sachsen	Sächsische Schweiz-	Altenberg	19,25	°C*days
Sachsen				69,95	

Figure 14: Different ways of data visualization that allow for multiple views

2.1.5 CONTACTS, FAQ AND GLOSSARY

The contacts, FAQ and glossary sections (currently under construction) are accessible from the footer of every page of the dashboard. Their goal is to help users better understand the content and functionalities of the dashboard.

Glossary

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Climate_CRICES

Term	Definition	Source
Biodiversity	Biodiversity or biological diversity means the variability among living organisms from all sources including, among other things, terrestrial, marine and other aquatic ecosystems , and the ecological complexes of which they are part; this includes diversity within species, between species and of ecosystems (UN, 1992).	https://apps.ipcc.ch/glossary/
Capacity	The combination of all the strengths,	https://www.undrr.org/drr-glossary/te

[Contacts](#)
[FAQ](#)

Powered by

Figure 15: Future implementation of the glossary in the site

2.2 MAIN FEATURES

The main features of the dashboard include:

- Multilingual accessibility
- Dynamic filtering
- Data export
- Visual report generation

2.2.1 MULTILINGUAL ACCESSIBILITY

One of the main requirements expressed by PPs is to make the dashboard accessible to public decision-makers in their own languages. Therefore, in the home page it is possible to switch languages and access the contents available in the selected language.

Currently the language switch is already available, but the non-English content is still missing since it is going to be produced by translation of the English content after the completion of the data uploads.

The screenshot shows the top navigation bar of the Climate_CRICES dashboard. A red box highlights the language selection menu, which includes the following options: Čeština, Deutsch, English (selected), Hrvatski, Italiano, Magyar, and Polski. The dashboard title is "Climate_CRICES dashboard". Below the title, there is a descriptive text: "This dashboard represents a synthesis of the existing regional data systems and it is aimed to support transborder and regional climate change management plans in Central Europe". The main content area features a map of Central Europe with a network of nodes and lines. At the bottom, there are four orange navigation buttons: "Regions", "Policies", "Impacts", and "Indicators". The footer contains links for "Contacts", "FAQ", and "Glossary", and a logo for "Powered by CSI".

Figure 16: Future implementation of the translation of all pages into all project site languages

2.2.2 DYNAMIC FILTERING

The adoption of Power BI as the technology to develop the dashboard also makes it possible to integrate some default functionalities of the tool such as dynamic filtering.

Each page of the dashboard can display interactive visual objects that allow users to dynamically interact with the content of the page with filters.

Figure 17: Different possibilities to filter through the data allow easy access to information

In this dashboard this functionality has also been adopted in order to dynamically interact with geographic visual objects, allowing dynamic filtering on static data sources (e.g. raster datasets).

Average Cooling Degree Days [1,2]

Figure 18: Geographic representation of data helps visualize information

Another important feature of Power BI dashboard is the possibility of applying filters across any of the visual objects of a given page.

Figure 19: Different types of diagrams and representations help grasp data and information

2.2.3 DATA EXPORTS

Another advantage of using a Power BI dashboard is that, for each visual object, it is possible to download the displayed data (with filters applied) in tabular format.

Figure 20: Export functions allow different data to be downloaded for further use.

2.2.4 VISUAL REPORT GENERATION

A functionality whose development is currently in progress and that is soon going to be available to users, is the possibility to download visual reports of any dashboard page (possibly with filters applied) in .pdf or image formats.

Figure 21: Different visual reports can help understanding the data and making them useful for further usage.

3 CONCLUSIONS

Deliverable D.1.4.2 marks a significant milestone in the Climate_CRICES project—the successful implementation of the first version of the data dashboard, integrating technical, strategic, and user-focused elements developed across the project's earlier phases.

The Climate_CRICES dashboard has been released in a first version that features the principal functionalities required by PPs, it is available to the general public without need of authentication and it provides access to the information about climate policies documents selected for the pilot regions of the project.

Building on the foundations laid in Deliverable D.1.3.1, which analysed the strengths and limitations of existing climate information platforms, the project identified key gaps in accessibility, policy integration, and interoperability, while recognising major strengths in detailed geospatial data and the availability of high-quality, sector-specific tools.

These findings directly informed the metadata structure, classification schemes, and indicator frameworks developed in Deliverable D.1.3.2 and shaped the design and functional priorities outlined in Deliverable D.1.3.3.

This deliverable demonstrates how these elements have been transformed into a working digital tool.

Key achievements include:

- A multilingual, user-friendly interface that makes climate change adaptation policies accessible, comparable and interpretable;
- Dynamic visualisations and policy-relevant comparisons across partner regions.

In the next project periods, the dashboard is going to be improved with additional functionalities and sections, by translating policies information and by uploading relevant datasets useful to monitor the implementation and the effects of the policies.